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(ICRTB 2024)

January 19-20, 2024

ABSTRACTS

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GreenNanoCure - Harnessing Oxidized Nano-Cellulose for Advanced Medicated Bandages

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Abstract: The innovative GreenNanoCure stands as a potentially groundbreaking solution in biomedical healthcare, ingeniously utilizing oxidized nano-cellulose sourced from agricultural waste to fabricate advanced medicated bandages. This transformative process involves extracting cellulose from agricultural residue, primarily crop stubble, and refining it into oxidized nano-cellulose, leading to the creation of bandages boasting exceptional hemostatic and therapeutic properties. This breakthrough has the potential to revolutionize wound care and infection control practices significantly. Targeting agro-waste, particularly wheat crop residue prevalent in regions like Punjab, Haryana, Delhi, and Uttarakhand, underscores the promising nature of this cellulose-rich waste for our project. The extraction methodology from materials such as sugarcane and rice straw undergoes crucial stages like boiling, bleaching, and oxidation, yielding vital oxidized nano-cellulose fibres pivotal for enhancing hemostasis and expediting blood clotting. Cellulose's significance lies in its remarkable hemostatic attributes, proving especially advantageous for diabetic patients grappling with inefficient blood clotting due to hyperglycemia. These bandages offer a viable solution by facilitating swift clotting, particularly beneficial for wounds in diabetic individuals. Additionally, for individuals afflicted with haemophilia, these bandages serve as an interim aid in blood clotting until professional medical care is accessible. Beyond specific medical conditions, these bandages boast broader applications, serving as an emergency solution for the general public, and augmenting access to efficient wound care. In military scenarios, these bandages exhibit immense potential by staunching bleeding and stabilizing injuries, a crucial intervention where immediate medical assistance might be logistically challenging. The

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ISBN 978-93-6039-051-8

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